

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of quinol, ascorbic acid and hydrogen peroxide by $[\text{Mn}_2^{\text{IV}}(\mu\text{-O})_2(\text{phen})_4]^{4+}$ ion[†]

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Abstract : The oxo-bridged dimanganese(IV,IV) complex, $[\text{Mn}_2^{\text{IV}}(\mu\text{-O})_2(\text{phen})_4]^{4+}$, $\{\mathbf{1}\}^{4+}$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) forms metastable solutions in dilute nitric acid media, where its UV-Vis spectra do not degrade for ~20 min. This solution quantitatively oxidizes ascorbic acid, quinol and hydrogen peroxide to dehydroascorbic acid, quinone and oxygen respectively. In general, each mole of the oxidant consumes two moles of reducing agent (H_2R), but stoichiometry depends on initial $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$. Under the first order conditions, maintained with excess (H_2R), a two-step irreversible consecutive kinetics leads the oxidant itself to Mn^{II} , at a rate much faster than auto-decomposition of the complex :

Among all the three H_2R , hydrogen peroxide reacts slowest. When H_2O_2 is added in low concentrations, some of the intermediate Mn_2^{III} are lost via auto-decomposition before advancing to the second (k_s) step and thus affects the stoichiometry. Protonated oxidants are more reactive than their conjugate bases, Mn_2^{IV} is more reactive than Mn_2^{III} and reactivity order of the reducing agents is : $\text{H}_2\text{A} \geq \text{H}_2\text{Q} \gg \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$. These observations are consistent with an outer sphere mechanism. The k_f step for ascorbic acid exhibits significant solvent isotope effect indicating an electroprotic process to be the rate-determining step of this path.

Keywords : Manganese(IV) oxidation, quinol, ascorbic acid, hydrogen peroxide, kinetics and mechanism.

Introduction

Manganese acts as an essential trace element¹, that shapes life as we see it. Bacterial oxidation² of Mn^{II} to Mn^{IV} is believed to drive the oxidative segment of the global biogeochemical manganese cycle and regulates the concentration of dissolved Mn^{II} in the oceanic water column, where it is a critical nutrient for planktonic primary productivity. The oxidation of water by photosynthetic enzymes (photosystem II; PSII)³, the reduction of ribonucleotides in certain bacteria⁴, and the disproportionation of hydrogen peroxide by some catalases or pseudocatalases⁵ have been shown to occur at bi- or polynuclear manganese containing active sites⁶.

Syntheses of bridged binuclear manganese complexes as also their chemical and physical properties have received significant attention, largely because of the impor-

tance of high-oxidation-state manganese species in biological systems and because of their potential use as redox catalysts⁷.

Following the successful isolation of the 1,10-phenanthroline complex, $[\text{Mn}_2^{\text{IV}}(\mu\text{-O})_2(\text{phen})_4]^{4+}$ ($\{\mathbf{1}\}^{4+}$; Fig. 1), a number of bis(μ -oxo)dimanganese(IV,IV) dimers

Fig. 1. A graphic structure of $\{\mathbf{1}\}^{4+}$, adopted from crystal structure¹⁰.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

of the type $[L_2Mn^{IV}O]_2^{4+}$ (L is a bidentate or tetradentate ligand) have now been synthesized and well characterized⁸. But till date, their solution chemistry seems mostly obscured.

Goodwin and Sylva⁹, who first synthesized the title complex $\{1\}^{4+}$ by the acid induced disproportionation of $[MnCl_3(H_2O)(phen)]^{2+}$ ion, also noted its instability in all common solvents. This might have some bearing on why solution chemistry of $\{1\}^{4+}$ remained unexplored till date.

We noticed that the UV-Vis spectra of $\{1\}^{4+}$ in dilute nitric acid ($\geq 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) suffered no change up to ~ 20 min; while its reactions with excess hydrogen peroxide, ascorbic acid and quinol are much faster. Stopped-flow technique allowed determination of fast kinetics of these reactions, because these went to completion much before any auto-decomposition of the complex.

This paper attempts to rationalize our kinetic, stoichiometric and UV-Vis spectral observations on these reactions.

Results and discussion

Preliminary observations : Aqueous $\{1\}^{4+}$, with or without added phen, is unstable and its UV-Vis spectra decay with time. However, in dilute HNO_3 ($\geq 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) spectra remained same for ~ 20 min (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, a reversible change in spectra with change in $[H^+]$ was noticeable. Such changes, albeit small (Fig. 2), happens only in the visible ($\lambda > 400 \text{ nm}$) not the UV-range, where both $Hphen^+$ and phen absorb strongly.

We infer that $\{1\}^{4+}$ suffers no acid catalysed aquation leading to release of coordinated phen in solution and

Fig. 2. Spectra of $\{1^{4+}\}$ in aqueous nitric acid media. $\{1^{4+}\}$, $0.20 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$, I , 1.0 mol dm^{-3} ($NaClO_4$); $[HNO_3]$, (1) 0.30 , (2) 0.20 , (3) 0.15 , (4) 0.10 mol dm^{-3} . These spectra suffered no change for ≥ 20 min. The slight variations in spectra with variations in $[HNO_3]$ are reversible.

that the observed spectral changes arise from oxo-bridge protonation – a phenomenon now well-documented^{11,12} in higher-valent manganese complexes. Cooper and Calvin¹¹ estimated $K_p \sim 10^{-2.5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for oxo-bridge protonation constant. We presume a smaller value for oxo-bridge protonation constant at $[Mn_2^{IV}(\mu-O)_2(phen)_4]^{4+}$.

Stoichiometry :

In general, each mole of $\{1\}^{4+}$ oxidized two moles of H_2R to R (see Table 1) :

A gas evolved when $\{1\}^{4+}$ oxidized hydrogen peroxide.

Table 1. Stoichiometry^a for the oxidation of H_2Q , H_2A and H_2O_2 by $\{1\}^{4+}$ in the presence of $[H_2R]_0 \geq 2.5 [\{1\}^{4+}]$

H_2R	$10^4 [\{1\}^{4+}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 [H_2R]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[H^+]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$\Delta[H_2R]/$ $\Delta[\{1\}^{4+}]$	$\Delta[H_2R]/\Delta[\{1\}^{4+}]$ avg.
H_2Q	5.0	15.0	0.10	1.97	1.99 ± 0.01
	5.0	20.0	0.10	1.98	
	5.0	30.0	0.25	1.99	
	10.0	30.0	0.30	2.01	
H_2A	4.0	15.0	0.15	2.08	2.02 ± 0.04
	4.0	20.0	0.15	1.99	
	10.0	30.0	0.20	1.98	
	15.0	50.0	0.25	2.03	
	5.0	20.0	0.10	2.05	
H_2O_2	5.0	20.0	0.20	1.98	2.0 ± 0.03
	5.0	40.0	0.30	1.97	
	10.0	40.0	0.30	1.97	

^aT 25 °C, total volume of the reaction mixture, 100 ml.

Alkaline pyrogallate almost completely absorbs the gas, which thus seems most likely to be O₂.

Observed stoichiometric ratio depends on initial [H₂O₂]. For example, Δ[H₂O₂]/Δ[{1}⁴⁺] is ~1 for the initial ratio [H₂O₂]₀/[{1}⁴⁺]₀ = 0.125–1.0 but increases to 2.0 for [H₂O₂]₀/[{1}⁴⁺]₀ > 2 (Table 2). Stoichiometric ratio, however, did not change for ascorbic acid or quinol. Neither did it change with the wavelength at which

Table 2. Stoichiometry^a for the oxidation of H₂O₂ by {1}⁴⁺ in the presence of [H₂R]₀ < 2 [{1}⁴⁺]₀

10 ⁴ [{1}⁴⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ [H ₂ R] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ R] ₀ /[{1}⁴⁺] ₀	Δ[H ₂ R]/Δ[{1}⁴⁺]
2.0	0.25	0.125	1.14
2.0	0.5	0.250	1.06
2.0	0.75	0.375	1.09
2.0	1.0	0.50	1.06
2.0	2.5	1.25	1.51
2.0	3.0	1.50	1.61
2.0	3.5	1.75	1.64
2.0	4.0	2.0	1.95

^aT 25 °C, total volume 100 ml.

{1}⁴⁺ is measured. With excess H₂R, the product solutions are very weakly colored and exhibit six-line EPR spectra characteristic for Mn^{II}. As conjectured, from the kinetic studies in the presence of excess H₂R, this Mn^{II} results from the reduction of {1}⁴⁺ via two-step irreversible, consecutive, first order (see eq. (2)) reactions :

$$A_t = A_\infty + a_f \exp(-k_f t) + a_s \exp(-k_s t) \quad (2b)$$

Eqs. (1) and (2a), together led us to speculate the following reaction pathways with H₂O₂ under the kinetic and the non-kinetic conditions :

(a) Under the kinetic conditions (large excess of H₂O₂ over [{1}⁴⁺]) :

(b) Under non-kinetic conditions ([H₂O₂] ~ [{1}⁴⁺]) :

In aqueous media, Mn₂^{III} complexes are unstable but the two reductants, H₂A and H₂Q react much faster. Plausibly, even low concentrations of H₂A and H₂Q rapidly

converts the intermediate Mn₂^{III} to Mn^{II}, permitting no time for Mn₂^{III} to go astray to the decomposition path. Hydrogen peroxide reacts slowest among the three reductants. Plausibly, the decomposition path successfully competes at low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide. This may be a reason why reaction stoichiometry for H₂O₂ but not for H₂A and H₂Q depends on the initial concentration.

Kinetics :

A_t-t data for ≥95% reaction yielded excellent fit to eq. (2b) (Fig. 3). First order rate constants, k_f and k_s thus evaluated have been presented in Table 3. Individual k_f and k_s could be reproduced within ±2% for duplicate runs.

Fig. 3. A typical fit of the A_t-t data to eq. 2(b) with k_f = 29.8 s⁻¹ and k_s = 3.4 s⁻¹. The solid line is the best fit to data points (256). The residual (expt.- calcd.) values are always sufficiently close to zero. [{1}⁴⁺] 0.20 mmol dm⁻³, [H₂Q] 4.0 mmol dm⁻³, [H⁺] 0.20 mol dm⁻³.

Both k_f and k_s increased linearly (eq. (3)) with increasing [H₂R], without any indication for rate saturation.

$$k_x = k'_x [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \quad (x = f \text{ or } s) \quad (3)$$

Experiments in D₂O-solvent isotope effect :

The k_f step in the reaction of ascorbic acid exhibited appreciable retardation in D₂O. For example, the k_f step in the reaction of 20.0 mmol dm⁻³ H₂A with 0.20 mmol dm⁻³ {1}⁴⁺ in 0.30 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ in aqueous media, was retarded by a factor of 3.68 in 94 mol% D₂O-H₂O media (k_{H₂O}/k_{D₂O} = 3.68). Neither k_f nor k_s for any other reaction changed appreciably. The results suggest that one proton and one electron are simultaneously

Table 3. First-order rate constants^a for the oxidation of excess H₂R by {1}⁴⁺ (0.20 mmol dm⁻³), T 25.0 °C, I 1.0 mol dm⁻³

[H ₂ R] (mmol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	k _f (s ⁻¹)	k _s (s ⁻¹)
H ₂ R = H ₂ A			
10	0.10	40.2 ± 0.6	3.50 ± 0.03
	0.15	41.6 ± 0.6	4.09 ± 0.09
	0.20	44.1 ± 0.3	4.57 ± 0.05
	0.25	44.6 ± 0.5	4.80 ± 0.05
	0.30	45.7 ± 0.1	5.67 ± 0.09
	0.35	48 ± 0.7	6.19 ± 0.07
4.0	0.20	29.4 ± 0.4	3.35 ± 0.03
5.0		35 ± 0.6	3.67 ± 0.05
6.0		39.4 ± 0.1	4.07 ± 0.01
7.0		42.1 ± 0.3	4.33 ± 0.04
8.0		43 ± 0.5	4.46 ± 0.03
10		44 ± 0.3	4.57 ± 0.05
H ₂ R = H ₂ Q			
4.0	0.10	103.6 ± 0.8	4.01 ± 0.06
	0.15	89.3 ± 0.6	4.41 ± 0.12
	0.20	75.4 ± 0.9	4.56 ± 0.07
	0.25	71.2 ± 0.8	4.81 ± 0.05
	0.30	66.4 ± 0.8	5.28 ± 0.18
	0.35	66.4 ± 0.8	5.28 ± 0.18
4.0	0.20	75.4 ± 0.9	4.56 ± 0.07
5.0		93.5 ± 0.8	5.07 ± 0.06
6.0		127 ± 3	5.62 ± 0.34
7.0		143 ± 5	6.0 ± 0.35
8.0		162 ± 3	6.29 ± 0.04
10		209 ± 4	14.8 ± 1.5
H ₂ R = H ₂ O ₂			
50	0.10	2.8 ± 0.2	5.5 ± 0.02
	0.15	3.0 ± 0.07	5.6 ± 0.03
	0.20	3.3 ± 0.02	5.7 ± 0.03
	0.25	3.38 ± 0.03	5.76 ± 0.02
	0.30	3.6 ± 0.04	5.8 ± 0.03
	0.35	3.8 ± 0.1	5.85 ± 0.02
	0.35	3.8 ± 0.1	5.85 ± 0.02
10	0.20	1.14 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.3
20		2.23 ± 0.4	3.14 ± 0.7
30		2.38 ± 0.04	3.43 ± 0.3
40		3.1 ± 0.06	5.2 ± 0.8
50		3.3 ± 0.02	5.70 ± 0.03
100		7.58 ± 0.07	15.0 ± 0.2

^aReported errors are standard deviations of a single run and indicative of goodness of fit of A_t-t data to eq. (2b). Duplicated runs reproduced individual rate constants within 5%.

transferred to {1}⁴⁺ at the rate-determining step of k_f in the reaction of ascorbic acid.

Reaction scheme for H₂A :

H₂Q (pK_{a1} 10)^{13a}, and H₂O₂ (pK_{a1} 11.82)^{13b} are very weak acids and under the experimental range of acidity be present exclusively as H₂Q and H₂O₂. Nevertheless, both H₂A and the HA⁻ forms of ascorbic acid [pK_{a1} (4.03), pK_{a2} (11.33)]^{14,15} exhibit significant kinetic activity even in moderately strong acidic media. Again, spectral observations stated above indicate reversible protonation at {1}⁴⁺. Therefore, two acid-base equilibria (4) and (5) appear relevant.

Following schemes most simply explain these spectral, equilibria and kinetic data :

The k_f step for ascorbic acid :

Assuming K₁[H⁺] << 1, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_f = \{(k_1 + K_1 K_a k_2) + k_3 K_a / [H^+]\} T_{H_2A}$$

Fig. 4. The variations in k_f and k_s with [H⁺] in the reaction of 0.20 mmol dm⁻³ {1}⁴⁺ with 10 mmol dm⁻³ H₂A; I, 1.0 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄), T 25.0 °C.

Fig. 5. Variations of k_f and k_s with $[H^+]$ in the reaction of $0.20 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3} \{1\}^{4+}$ with $4.0 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3} \text{H}_2\text{Q}$; I , $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4)$, T $25.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Excellent linearity of k_f vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ plot (see Fig. 5) supports the scheme. Absence of any $[H^+]^2$ -term in Fig. 5 justified elimination of the $\{1\text{H}\}^{5+}$ - H_2A -path from the scheme. The k_1 and the k_3 paths are electroprotic; k_2 is not. Moreover, k_2 is proton ambiguous with k_1 . Thus, unambiguous conclusion on the presence or otherwise of k_2 in k_f seems impossible.

The k_s step for ascorbic acid :

Assuming $K_2 [H^+] \ll 1$, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_s = \{(k_4 + K_2 K_5 k_5) + K_2 k_6 [H^+]\} T_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}$$

A linear dependence of k_s on $[H^+]$ and absence of any $[H^+]^2$ -term was verified (Fig. 5).

We propose slightly different schemes for the other two reductants, viz. hydrogen peroxide and quinol because (1) neither HO_2^- nor HQ^- contributes to kinetics and because (2) unlike H_2A , neither H_2O_2 nor H_2Q follows electroprotic path.

The k_f step for quinol (H_2Q) :

Assuming $K_1 \ll [H^+]$, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_f = \{k_7 + K_1 k_8 [H^+]\} T_{\text{H}_2\text{Q}}$$

Its experimental validity was verified (Fig. 4).

The k_s step for quinol (H_2Q) :

Assuming $K_2 \ll [H^+]$, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_s = \{k_9 + (K_2)^{-1} k_{10} [H^+]\} T_{\text{H}_2\text{Q}}$$

This was experimentally verified (see Fig. 4).

The k_f step for hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) :

Assuming $K_1 \ll [H^+]$, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_f = \{k_{11} + K_1 k_{12} [H^+]\} T_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$$

This was experimentally verified (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Variation of k_f with $[H^+]$ in the reaction of $0.20 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3} \{1\}^{4+}$ with $50 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3} \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$; I , $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4)$, T $25.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The k_s step for hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) :

Assuming $K_2 \ll [H^+]$, this reaction sequence leads to :

$$k_s = \{k_{13} + K_2 k_{14} [H^+]\} T_{H_2O_2}$$

This was experimentally verified (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Variation in k_s with $[H^+]$ in the reaction of $0.20 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ $\{1\}^{4+}$ with 50 mmol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 ; $I, 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaClO_4$), $T 25.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The observed dependences of k_f and k_s on $[H^+]$ have been summarized in Table 4 along with the derived val-

ues for the rate constants defined by the schemes above.

In Table 4, two sets of rate constants appear in pairs, k_1, k_2 and k_4, k_5 . They cannot be separated due to proton ambiguity in the reaction with ascorbic acid. Nevertheless, if K_1 and $1/K_2$ are very small, following conclusions may be reached :

(i) Protonated oxidants are more reactive than their conjugate bases.

(ii) Mn_2^{IV} is more reactive than Mn_2^{III} .

(iii) Order of reaction rate is : $H_2A \geq H_2Q \gg H_2O_2$.

We could not compare the reactivity of H_2A vs HA^- , due to proton ambiguity. Nevertheless, conclusions i-iii above, suggest a strong correlation between reactivity and thermodynamic redox strengths of the reactants, thus implying an outer sphere pathway.

This seems likely for $\{1\}^{4+}$ is co-ordinatively saturated and it is substitution inert even under the acidic conditions used here. Outer-sphere reactions are rare for H_2O_2 .

Nevertheless, the high thermodynamic oxidizing power of $\{1\}^{4+}$ probably pays for the cost, as found earlier with the reaction of H_2O_2 with $[Ni(bipy)_3]^{3+}$.

Experimental

Materials :

The dark-red, air stable pure solid complex, $\{1\}(ClO_4)_4 \cdot H_2O$ was prepared as described by Goodwin and Sylva⁹.

Table 4. Rate constants and composite constants for the oxidation of quinol, ascorbic acid and hydrogen peroxide by $[Mn_2^{IV}(\mu-O)_2(phen)_4]^{4+}$

R	Observed dependences of k_f and k_s on $[H^+]$ and $[H_2R]$	Rate constants ^a	Reactant pairs
H_2A	$k_f = \{(k_1 + K_1 K_a k_2) + k_3 K_a / [H^+]\} T_{H_2A}$ $k_s = \{(k_4 + K_2 K_a k_5) + K_2 k_6 [H^+]\} T_{H_2A}$	$(k_1 + K_1 K_a k_2) = (1.21 \pm 0.05) \times 10^4 \text{ }^b$ $k_3 K_a = (1.42 \pm 0.01) \times 10^3 \text{ }^b$ $(k_4 + K_2 K_a k_5) = (8.62 \pm 0.37) \times 10^2 \text{ }^b$ $K_2 k_6 = (1.4 \pm 0.13) \times 10^3 \text{ }^b$	$(\{1\}^{4+} - H_2A + \{1H\}^{5+} - HA^-)$ $(\{1\}^{4+} - HA^-)$ $(\{1\}^{2+} - H_2A + \{1H\}^{3+} - HA^-)$ $(\{1H\}^{3+} - H_2A)$
H_2Q	$k_f = \{k_7 + K_1 k_8 [H^+]\} T_{H_2Q}$ $k_s = \{k_9 + K_2 k_{10} [H^+]\} T_{H_2Q}$	$k_7 = (3.73 \pm 0.06) \times 10^3 \text{ }^b$ $K_1 k_8 = (2.96 \pm 0.25) \times 10^3 \text{ }^c$ $k_9 = (2.43 \pm 0.12) \times 10^2 \text{ }^b$ $K_2 k_{10} = (1.05 \pm 0.07) \times 10^3 \text{ }^c$	$(\{1\}^{4+} - H_2Q)$ $(\{1H\}^{5+} - H_2Q)$ $(\{1\}^{2+} - H_2Q)$ $(\{1H\}^{3+} - H_2Q)$
H_2O_2	$k_f = \{k_{11} + K_1 k_{12} [H^+]\} T_{H_2O_2}$ $k_s = \{k_{13} + K_2 k_{14} [H^+]\} T_{H_2O_2}$	$k_{11} = (4.8 \pm 0.16) \text{ }^b$ $K_1 k_{12} = (7.6 \pm 0.6) \text{ }^c$ $k_{13} = (1.1 \pm 0.01) \text{ }^b$ $K_2 k_{14} = (0.28 \pm 0.03) \text{ }^c$	$(\{1\}^{4+} - H_2O_2)$ $(\{1H\}^{5+} - H_2O_2)$ $(\{1\}^{2+} - H_2O_2)$ $(\{1H\}^{3+} - H_2O_2)$

^aStoichiometric factor ignored, ^bdm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, ^cdm⁶ mol⁻² s⁻¹.

Yield 76%, on the basis of $[\text{MnCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{phen})]$ (Found : C, 44.9; H, 3.1; Cl, 10.9; N, 8.7; Mn, 8.5. Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{32}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: C, 45.1; H, 2.7; N, 8.8; Mn, 8.6%).

The starting material $[\text{MnCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{phen})]$, in turn, was prepared from KMnO_4 and phenanthroline monohydrate in 10 N HCl. Yield 5.5 g (25.9% on the basis of KMnO_4). 1,4-Dihydroxybenzene (hydroquinone, quinol, m.p. 176°; A.R.; B.D.H.) was crystallized from acetonitrile (25 g in 30 ml) under nitrogen, dried under vacuum¹⁶ and stored at 0 °C. 1,10-Phenanthroline monohydrate and ascorbic acid were from E. Merck and used as such. Solution of hydrogen peroxide were prepared by dilution of 30% (w/v), stabilizer free H_2O_2 (G.R., E. Merck) and standardised by iodometry¹⁷. Nitrogen saturated solutions of ascorbic acid, hydroquinone and the complex were prepared just prior to use. Solutions of $\{1\}(\text{ClO}_4)_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in HNO_3 , when in use, were renewed every 10 min. Solutions of H_2O_2 were estimated just prior to their use in kinetic and stoichiometric measurements. NaNO_3 and NaClO_4 solutions used to maintain ionic strength were prepared and standardised as described earlier¹⁸. Throughout the work doubly distilled water was used.

Product(s) and stoichiometry :

Stoichiometries for reactions with an initial ratio, $[\text{H}_2\text{R}]_0 : [\{1\}^{4+}]_0 \geq 2.5$ (Table 1), were measured by determination of the residual $[\text{H}_2\text{R}]$ in the product mixture. For example, quinol in the product mixture was quantified by hydroxylamine-cerriic technique¹⁹ at 380 nm.

Ascorbic acid was determined²⁰ using its reaction with 4-methoxy-2-nitrobenzenediazonium chloride. The product is intense blue (λ_{max} 570 nm) in alkaline solution. Hydrogen peroxide was determined²¹ by its reaction with titanyl(IV) oxalate. The gas evolved during the reaction of H_2O_2 with $\{1\}^{4+}$ was passed through an alkaline pyrogallate solution in a micro-burette.

For reactions with initial $[\text{H}_2\text{R}]_0 : [\{1\}^{4+}]_0$ ratio < 2, (Table 2) the residual $[\{1\}^{4+}]$ was calculated from its known molar extinction coefficient (e.g. $\epsilon = 2350 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 420 nm).

Physical measurements and kinetics :

The kinetics was determined at 25.0 °C with a HITECH-500 and a Bio-Logic SFM3 stopped-flow spectrophotometers, following, at 420 nm, the disappearance of $\{1\}^{4+}$ in (0.10–0.30) mol dm^{-3} HNO_3 , I , 1.0 mol dm^{-3} (NaNO_3). Large excess (≥ 20 fold) of the reducing agents (H_2R) over $[\{1\}^{4+}]$ ensured first-order conditions. The

A_t-t data (256) yielded excellent fit to eq. 2(b) for a sequence of two, irreversible, consecutive first-order reactions. In this equation, k_f and k_s are the pseudo-first-order rate constants for the fast and the slow reaction respectively; a_f and a_s are corresponding amplitudes in units of absorbance. Standard deviations (in k_f and k_s) of the single kinetic runs were $\leq 1\%$.

$$A_t = A_\infty + a_f \exp(-k_f t) + a_s \exp(-k_s t) \quad (2b)$$

The first-order rate constants k_f and k_s were evaluated by treating the points of a single run with a weighed least-squares program.

All spectral and non-kinetic data were recorded with a Shimadzu (1601 PC) UV-Vis spectrophotometer, using 1 cm quartz cells.

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